

EMPOWERING STARTUP ECOSYSTEM IN INDIA: A CASE STUDY APPROACH

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Abstract : India boasts the distinction of being the third-largest startup ecosystem globally, a testimony to its vibrant entrepreneurial landscape. Several interwoven factors contribute to this remarkable growth trajectory. First and foremost, the proliferation of automation and widespread adoption of technology play pivotal roles. Increased internet penetration and soaring mobile consumption further fuel the momentum, creating fertile ground for innovative ventures to flourish. Support structures like startup incubation programs coupled with government schemes such as Skill India and Digital India, bolster the startup ecosystem's resilience and sustainability. The burgeoning pool of investments, both domestic and foreign, underscores investor confidence and further propels the ecosystem's growth trajectory. This present article shares the intricacies of establishing and managing startups, highlighting key initiatives taken by the Government of India. Through the lens of real-life case studies from the Indian startup landscape, it offers insights into the challenges and strategies that drive entrepreneurial ventures in the country.

Introduction

In August 2015, Narendra Modi the Prime Minister unveiled the Start-up India initiative at the historic Red Fort, with Finance Minister Arun Jaitley officially launching it on January 16, 2016. This visionary initiative aims to offer comprehensive support to budding entrepreneurs and nascent businesses. Recognizing the manifold challenges faced by new ventures—ranging from financial constraints to regulatory hurdles—the government pledges to extend aid across multiple domains, including finance, technology, economics, social welfare, and environmental sustainability.

The Start-up India initiative serves as a much-needed beacon of assistance from the Indian government, facilitating the realization of innovative ideas into tangible business ventures. Many successful startups have emerged from crises, with enterprising individuals seizing the moment to turn challenges into opportunities. However, the path from idea to enterprise is not without its pitfalls. Without effective management and strategic foresight, even the most promising ventures may falter along the way.

According to a study conducted by the UK-based accounting firm Sage, the Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs) have earned the prestigious distinction of being ranked as the world's fourth-largest contributors to billion-dollar startups. Among these groundbreaking ventures are industry titans like Ola, Snapdeal, Zomato, ShopClues and Flipkart.

Key highlights depicting the existing state of startups in India:

- India stands proudly as the third-largest startup hub globally, indicative of its dynamic entrepreneurial environment
- The average age of startup founders in India is a youthful 27 years, underscoring the enthusiasm and energy of young entrepreneurs
- While there's still progress to be made, 18% startup founders in India are women, marking a positive trend to greater gender diversity and inclusivity in the startup ecosystem.
- The total number of recognized startups in India has soared from a meagre 471 in 2016 to an impressive 72,993 in 2022, reflecting the exponential expansion and diversity of innovative ventures across various sectors.
- Women-owned enterprises, once a minority, are on a remarkable trajectory towards constituting a significant 33% of all businesses by 2030. This growth is projected to substantially increase the numeral of women-owned enterprises from 13.5-15.7 million in 2016 to a staggering 31.5 million in the coming years, highlighting the pivotal role of females in driving India's entrepreneurial landscape.

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Literature Review

Jain.S (2016) in her study entitled "Growth of Startup Ecosystem in India" discovered that the great problems of Indian startup are fragmented and unorganised market and absence of exposure to communication sources. India's burgeoning start-up ecosystem has captured global acclaim, as an increasing number of talented young individuals are choosing to pursue their entrepreneurial ambitions instead of opting for traditional career paths in large corporations or government sectors. (Sridevi and Babu (2019)). They explored the challenges of startups, numerous government initiatives and opportunities of startup and mentioned the challenges ranging from finance to human resource.

Shijith (2019) study titled "Examining Awareness of Start-ups Among Higher Education Students in Kannur District, Kerala" aimed to gauge the level of awareness regarding start-ups among students in higher education and to understand their inclination towards self-employment. The findings revealed that a significant portion of respondents expressed interest in exploring new opportunities, although they exhibited only partial awareness of government policies related to start-ups.

The focal point underscores the importance of facilitating easy initiation and closure processes, especially given the high rate of start-up failures (Chandiok, Suniti (2016)). The research paper "India the World's Fastest Growing Startup Ecosystem: A Study." discovered that respondents endorsed the concept of providing funding for incubation centres. The Government's proposal to implement such funding initiatives across universities, innovation hubs, research parks, and industrial zones aligns with these sentiments.

Pandey (2018) investigated the dynamics of entrepreneurial ecosystems within Indian metropolitan areas, emphasizing the factors influencing startup funding. The research sheds light on how entrepreneurial market insights can enhance the overall effectiveness of the ecosystem.

The study by Sushil, kamala Kannan (2019) delved into the examination of diverse strategic innovation factors (Innovative firm infrastructure, resource management, team learning) across two distinct startups, assessing their performance in service-oriented versus product-oriented enterprises. Understanding these innovative elements is paramount for startups as they navigate the challenging initial phase and strive for sustained growth.

Despite facing numerous challenges, startup enterprises have persistently expanded their operations. Both state and central governments are actively working to alleviate these hurdles, displaying remarkable enthusiasm through the implementation of impactful schemes such as 'MAKE IN INDIA', 'STARTUP INDIA', 'MUDRA YOJNA', and 'E-BIZ PORTAL'. These initiatives not only facilitate the growth of startups but also contribute significantly to elevating the GDP from its grassroots to a commendable level (Vandana, Susheela (2022))

Research Objectives

- Exploring the Government of India's Initiatives Supporting Startup Companies.
- Highlighting Successful Startup Case Studies as Learning Examples.

Methodology

To accomplish the objective of the study, thus gathered insights from leading scholars, industry experts, and thought leaders through a comprehensive review of academic literature, conference publications, edited collections, and think tank analyses. The research adopts a descriptive and conceptual approach.

Government of India's Initiatives Supporting Startup Companies

Startup India Initiative: This initiative revolutionizes regulatory landscapes by embracing self-certification and relaxing compliance norms. With over 58,000 startups were empowered, lead to creation of an estimated 1.75 lakh jobs.

Startup India Seed Fund Scheme (SISFS): Pioneering financial support to budding ventures, SISFS extends a lifeline with grants of up to ₹10 crore through accredited incubators.

Credit Guarantee Scheme for Startups(CGSS): Removing the financial hurdles, CGSS facilitates access to credit, propelling over 7,300 startups forward with sanctioned loans exceeding an enormous ₹29,500 crore.

Atal Innovation Mission (AIM): AIM empowers innovators with grants of up to ₹10 crore, leading to the launch of Tinkering Labs and Atal Incubation Centers nationwide, fostering an environment conducive to innovation and growth.

Software Technology Parks of India (STPI): STPI offers indispensable tax benefits, infrastructure support, and incubation facilities, nurturing the expansion of over 85,000 STPI units and fostering technological advancement.

Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana (PMMY): PMMY empowers entrepreneurs with collateral-free loans ranging from ₹50,000 to ₹10 lakh.

Ebiz Portal: This single-window platform streamlines processes, saving precious time and effort for entrepreneurs. With over 1.3 crore registrations processed, it serves as a testament to efficiency and ease of doing business.

Dairy Processing and Infrastructure Development Fund (DIDF): DIDF extends financial assistance for the establishment and expansion of dairy processing units, bolstering the dairy industry's infrastructure and capabilities.

Startup Intellectual Property Protection Scheme (SIPPS): SIPPS incentivizes IP protection by reimbursing startups 50% of filing fees for patents, trademarks, and copyrights, fostering a culture of innovation and safeguarding intellectual assets.

Market Access Promotion Scheme (MAPS): Paving the way for global outreach, MAPS facilitates international trade fair participation, providing financial assistance to unlock new markets and opportunities, fostering expansion and growth on a global scale

Case Study 1: OLA

Ola Cabs, an Indian multinational ridesharing corporation headquartered in Bangalore, has diversified its business interests beyond transportation services to include financial services and cloud kitchens. Notable venture capitalists, including Softbank, hold substantial stakes in the company. Founded by Bhavish Aggarwal and Ankit Bhati, Ola operates as a comprehensive ride-hailing platform, connecting users with local drivers via a mobile application. The platform offers various transportation options, ranging from economy to premium rides, auto-rickshaws, bikes, and shared rides. Ola's international footprint extends to countries such as Australia, New Zealand, and the United Kingdom.

Aside from conventional ride-hailing services, Ola provides a range of specialized offerings, including Ola Auto (auto-rickshaws), Ola Bike (motorbike rides), Ola Share (ride-sharing), and Ola Rentals (hourly vehicle rentals). The company has ventured into the electric mobility sector with Ola Electric, focusing on electric scooters and associated charging infrastructure. Ola has garnered substantial funding from prominent investors like SoftBank, Tencent, among others, resulting in a valuation amounting to billions of dollars, solidifying its position as a leader in the ride-hailing and mobility industry.

Mission Statement

- To provide best transport services

Ola Vision Statement

- Be the leader
- Ola Values Effectiveness Creativity Modernization Efficiency

Milestone Timeline of Ola's Evolution:

- Inception (December 2010): Ola commenced its journey in December 2010 in Mumbai, India, initially as an online cab aggregator service.
- Expansion Across India (2011-2014): Ola gradually extended its services to various major cities across India, emerging as one of the foremost ride-hailing platforms in the nation.
- Introduction of Ola Mobile App (2011): The launch of the Ola mobile app in 2011 revolutionized the booking process, offering users the convenience of booking rides through their smartphones.

- Diversification with Ola Auto and Ola Mini (2014): Ola broadened its service portfolio by introducing Ola Auto for booking auto-rickshaws and Ola Mini for more economical car rides.
- International Endeavours (2015): Ola ventured into international markets, launching its services in Australia, the United Kingdom, and other regions. However, it later redirected its focus primarily to the Indian market.
- Introduction of Ola Money (2015): Ola introduced Ola Money, a digital wallet facilitating cashless transactions for rides and other services.
- Acquisition of TaxiForSure (2015): Ola bolstered its market presence and expanded its customer base by acquiring TaxiForSure, another prominent Indian ride-hailing company.
- Foray into Electric Mobility (2017): Ola embraced sustainability by entering the electric vehicle domain with Ola Electric, aiming to promote eco-friendly transportation solutions.
- Strategic Investment from SoftBank (2017): SoftBank, a renowned Japanese conglomerate, made a substantial investment in Ola, further fortifying its financial position.
- Launch of Ola Play (2016): Ola introduced Ola Play, an innovative in-car entertainment platform, enhancing passenger experience through interactive and personalized features.
- Investment in Vogo (2019): Ola diversified its interests by investing in Vogo, a startup specializing in scooter rentals, signalling its broader involvement in the mobility and transportation sector.
- Ola's IPO Announcement (2021): In 2021, Ola announced its intention to go public with an initial public offering (IPO), marking a momentous milestone in its transition to a publicly traded company.

Marketing Strategies

- Digital Marketing and Social Media
- Ola Money Wallet Promotions
- In-Car Entertainment (Ola Play)
- Partnerships and Collaborations:
- Investments in Electric Vehicles:
- Data-Driven Personalization:

Investments Of OLA

- SoftBank Group: SoftBank Group, a prominent Japanese multinational conglomerate, provided substantial funding to Ola across multiple funding rounds.
- Tencent Holdings, a leading Chinese technology conglomerate, invested in Ola as part of its global initiative to bolster ride-hailing platforms.

- During various funding rounds, Ola garnered investment support from renowned institutions such as Warburg Pincus, a prominent international private equity firm, and Sequoia Capital, a distinguished global venture capital firm. Additionally, institutional investors like GIC (formerly known as Government of Singapore Investment Corporation) and Matrix Partners India also contributed to Ola's funding endeavours.

Parameters	Ola
Market Share (2022)	59%
Total Downloads (as of 2022)	550 million+
Monthly active users (as of 2022)	100 million+
Total Revenue (2022)	\$8.5 billion
YOY Growth (2022)	42%
Primary Revenue Source	Ride-Hailing
Secondary Revenue Source	Food delivery

Social Media Marketing strategy

- Twitter serves as Ola's platform for real-time updates, announcements, and customer service engagement.
- Ola maintains an active presence on Facebook, utilizing it for sharing promotional content, company announcements, and customer stories.
- On Instagram, Ola's account emphasizes visual content, showcasing images to engage its audience.
- Ola's LinkedIn presence is geared towards business-oriented content, sharing updates on partnerships and other professional aspects.

Case Study 2: NYKAA

Nykaa, an Indian e-commerce enterprise specializing in wellness and beauty products, was established by Falguni Nayar in 2012. Since its commencement, Nykaa has emerged as a prominent online destination for beauty and cosmetic shopping in India. The company's diverse product catalogue encompasses skincare, makeup, hair care, fragrances, and more, showcasing a blend of both international and domestic brands. Nykaa has further broadened its offerings by introducing its private label, featuring a range of beauty and skincare products under the brand name "Nykaa." Renowned for its user-friendly website and app, expansive product assortment, and customer-centric approach, Nykaa has garnered widespread acclaim and popularity among consumers.

Vision: Bring inspiration and joy to people, everywhere, every day.

SHARE PRICE OF NYKAA (in Rupee)

Balance sheet of Nykaa

Milestones of Nykaa are:

- Nykaa boasts over 1.2 lakh products from 1900+ brands as of January 2024.
- Nykaa has occupied more than 5 million square feet of warehouse space as of January 2024.
- With a user base exceeding \$21 million as of November 2023,
- It has a total of 141 store counts as of 2022.
- 40 fulfilment centres in 18 cities as of 2022.
- 105 stores across India as of 2022.
- 23 warehouses across 11 Indian cities.

Marketing Strategy of Nykaa

- Wide Product Range
- Private Label Products
- Customer Loyalty Programs
- Sales and Discounts
- User-friendly Website and App
- Offline Presence

Investment Partnerships of Nykaa Include:

- Fidelity Investments: Nykaa secured funding from Fidelity Investments in a Series F funding round in 2020.
- Steadview Capital: In 2019, Steadview Capital, an esteemed investment firm, participated in a funding round supporting Nykaa's growth.
- TPG Growth: Nykaa garnered investment from TPG Growth, a reputable private equity firm, in 2018.
- Lighthouse Funds: Earlier in its development, Nykaa received investment from Lighthouse Funds during a funding round.

Social Media Marketing

- Nykaa leverages its robust presence on Instagram, showcasing visually captivating content to engage its audience.

- On Facebook, Nykaa operates an active page, sharing a blend of promotional content, beauty tips, and updates.
- Twitter serves as Nykaa's platform for swift updates and announcements, ensuring timely communication with its audience.
- Influencer Partnerships:
- User-Generated Content (UGC)

Conclusion

According to NASSCOM report India is securing the third position in the global startup ecosystem, marking a momentous milestone in the nation's entrepreneurial journey. The startup landscape in India is prospering at an exponential rate, analogous to the growth of a grapevine. This advancement is propelled by the country's dynamic economic landscape, characterized by the implementation of liberal policies and initiatives such as 'Make in India', 'Startup India', and 'Mudra', among others. The government of India is enthusiastically fostering an environment favourable to entrepreneurial success, with an aim to bolster the country's economic development from the grassroots level. In line with this vision, initiatives targeted at startups offer accelerated approval processes, streamlined exit mechanisms, tax incentives, and shortened patent registrations. These procedures jointly contribute to a flourishing ecosystem where startups can transform, nurture, grow and contribute significantly to India's GDP trajectory.

References

- Surbhi Jain (2016), Growth of Startup Ecosystem in India, *International Journal of Applied Research*,2(2), 152-154.
- Chandiok, Suniti (2016), India the World's Fastest Growing Startup Ecosystem: A Study, *Amity Research Journal of Tourism, Aviation and Hospitality*,1(2),84-93.
- Shijith.V(2019), A Study on Awareness of Startup Among Students in Higher Education with Special Reference to Kanur District Kerala, *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*,6(2), 95-96.
- Neeraj Pandey (2018), An Analysis of Start-up Ecosystem in Metropolitan City in India, *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*,8(2)
- Kamala Kannan, Sushil (2019), Strategic innovation factors in startups: results of a cross-case analysis of Indian start-ups, *Journal of Global Business Advancement*, 12(03)
- Dr. Vandana, Dr. Susheela (2022), Startups-A New Paradigm for Young Entrepreneurs,*International Journal of Engineering, Business and Management*,6(5) <https://dx.doi.org/10.22161/ijebm.6.5>
- S. P. Robbins, *Organizational Behavior, Motivation concepts* Pearson Education, 2009, 194.
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Start-up_company
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Start-up_India
- http://www.iisermohali.ac.in/Start-upIndia_ActionPlan_16January2016.pdf
- <https://www.speakingwalls.in/blogs/speaking-walls/85632515-eight-challenges-faced-by-an-indian-start-up>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/top-10-government-schemes-startups-india-favcy-nenqf>
- <https://g.co/finance/NYKAA:NSE>
- <https://appicsoftwares.com/nykaa-revenue-and-user-statistics/>
- <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1053514/nykaa-revenue/>